

The Role of Ketogenic and Glucogenic Amino Acids in Ketogenesis

A Biochemical Perspective on Amino Acid Profiles and Ketone Body Production

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Abstract

The ketogenic diet has gained prominence in recent years and is increasingly recognized as an effective strategy for improving health and preventing disease. While fats, particularly medium-chain triglycerides (MCTs), play a key role in ketogenesis, the importance of amino acids is often overlooked.

Based on biochemical metabolic pathways, this paper discusses the potential role of ketogenic and glucogenic amino acids in the context of the ketogenic diet and formulates a hypothesis regarding targeted amino acid composition. Furthermore, glucogenic and neutral amino acids and their conversion to glucose are described in detail to illustrate how they might potentially influence ketogenesis and promote gluconeogenesis. In addition, the role of BCAAs and EAAs in the ketogenic diet is analyzed to investigate possible disadvantages for ketogenesis.

1. Introduction

The ketogenic diet has gained increasing prominence both among the general public and within the scientific community. It is regarded not only as an effective method for weight loss but also as a therapeutic approach for epilepsy, diabetes, and neurodegenerative diseases.

Originally developed in the 1920s to treat childhood epilepsy, the ketogenic diet has evolved into a significant component of modern dietary approaches aimed at improving metabolic health and reducing the risk of chronic diseases. At its core, the ketogenic diet is based on drastically reducing carbohydrate intake while increasing fat consumption to put the body into a state of ketogenesis. During ketogenesis, the body converts fatty acids in particular, but also certain amino acids, into ketone bodies, which serve as an alternative energy source for the brain and other tissues. This metabolic process triggers a series of biochemical reactions that influence both energy production and the regulation of blood sugar levels.

Despite the widely recognized benefits of fats, particularly medium-chain triglycerides (MCTs), in ketogenesis, the role of amino acids is often overlooked. Amino acids are not only the building blocks of proteins but also play a crucial role in numerous biochemical processes in the body. Particular focus is

placed on the amino acids leucine, lysine, phenylalanine, and tyrosine, as their metabolic pathways are closely linked to the formation of acetyl-CoA and thus have the potential to contribute to ketone body production. Based on the biochemical literature, a conceptual framework is proposed that describes these amino acids as a functional group. In this work, this group is referred to as “KCAA.”

The term KCAA[®] (Ketogenic Chain Amino Acids) has been registered as a trademark to safeguard the scientific basis of the concept and the integrity of the product, and to promote its use in research. The focus is on further developing approaches that advance metabolic health and research.

This work should therefore be interpreted as a hypothesis-generating model and not as an experimentally confirmed metabolic mechanism. Further experimental and clinical studies are needed to investigate the actual metabolic influence of specific amino acid combinations under conditions of a ketogenic diet.

The lead author is the developer of the KCAA formulation discussed in this paper. This article presents a theoretical and literature-based analysis aimed at discussing possible biochemical mechanisms and formulating hypotheses for future research.

Conceptual Framework: The Role of Amino Acids in Ketogenesis

The following conceptual framework illustrates the metabolic relationships discussed in this paper. It should be understood as a theoretical model that visualizes possible metabolic interactions. Further experiments are needed to confirm the theoretical mechanisms.

Fig. 1 This model illustrates the potential role of various amino acids in energy production under ketogenic metabolic conditions.

Sports Applications and Benefits of Ketogenesis

The ketogenic diet has not only proven effective in clinical settings but has also found widespread use outside the medical field. In recent years, the ketogenic diet has become a popular choice for people looking to improve their overall health or lose weight. Particularly noteworthy is the growing interest in the ketogenic diet in competitive sports. A large number of professional athletes and coaches now rely on this dietary approach to benefit from optimized fat burning and a more stable energy supply through ketone bodies. The ketogenic diet allows athletes to rely on an alternative energy source derived from the conversion of fats into ketone bodies. For endurance athletes such as marathon runners, cyclists, or triathletes, ketogenesis offers the advantage of reducing the strain on glycogen stores while simultaneously maintaining a stable energy supply during prolonged exertion. Unlike the body's carbohydrate stores, which are quickly depleted during intense activity, ketone bodies provide a continuous energy supply and thus help delay the onset of fatigue.

For sports that require rapid recovery periods and improved regenerative capacity, such as weightlifting, CrossFit, or track and field, the ketogenic diet also offers potential benefits. By lowering insulin levels and reducing inflammatory markers, athletes can recover more quickly after intense training, and the loss of muscle mass is minimized. Furthermore, recent studies show that the ketogenic diet can reduce the production of free radicals during exercise, which positively impacts cellular health and recovery.

Another interesting aspect is the potential effect of the ketogenic diet on mental performance and concentration. In intense competitive situations that require a high degree of mental focus, ketone bodies can serve as a constant energy source for the brain, thereby preventing fluctuations in performance. This could be particularly advantageous in sports such as chess, esports, or competitive shooting, where peak performance is required not only physically but also cognitively.

This potential has brought the ketogenic diet into the spotlight, particularly the role of ketogenic amino acids (KCAAs), as these not only promote ketogenesis but may also offer benefits for muscle recovery and development.

2. Ketogenic Amino Acids in Detail

Ketogenic amino acids play a unique role in energy metabolism during ketogenesis, as they contribute directly or indirectly to the formation of ketone bodies. These ketone bodies - particularly acetoacetate and β -hydroxybutyrate (BHB) - provide a stable energy source that can be utilized by the brain, muscles, and other tissues. The four ketogenic amino acids leucine, lysine, phenylalanine, and tyrosine are distinguished by their ability to be converted directly or indirectly into ketone bodies.

Fig.2 The carbon skeleton can be converted entirely or largely into ketone bodies.

2.1 L-Leucine: Pathway to ketogenesis and muscle protein synthesis

Leucine is one of the best-known ketogenic amino acids and plays a key role in ketogenesis. It is primarily converted in the liver via transamination and subsequent oxidative decarboxylation into acetyl-CoA, which then contributes to the formation of ketone bodies. Through the production of acetyl-CoA, leucine becomes a direct source of ketone bodies and is therefore particularly well-suited for maintaining ketogenesis. (Sato et al., 2006)

An additional benefit of leucine is its ability to promote muscle protein synthesis by activating the mTOR (mammalian Target of Rapamycin) signaling pathway. As a result, leucine can promote muscle growth, which is particularly valuable for athletes following a ketogenic diet. (Volek et al., 2009)

2.2 L-Lysine: An Essential Building Block for Ketone Bodies Production and Tissue Regeneration

Lysine is an essential amino acid that plays a key role in energy metabolism and protein synthesis. Compared to leucine, lysine is preferentially converted to β -hydroxybutyrate (BHB), one of the most important ketone bodies. The conversion of lysine into ketone bodies begins with the formation of acetoacetyl-CoA, which is broken down into acetyl-CoA and then converted into BHB.

(Takamura, T., Et al., 2011)

Lysine is also involved in tissue repair, which aids in recovery after physical exertion. Studies show that lysine may have antioxidant effects that contribute to cellular health and potentially reduce the oxidative stress that occurs during intense physical activity.

2.3 L-Phenylalanine: Strong ketone bodies formation and neurotransmitter synthesis

Phenylalanine is an essential amino acid that serves not only as a ketogenic amino acid but also as a precursor for the synthesis of tyrosine and several important neurotransmitters. During ketogenesis, phenylalanine is converted through a series of enzymatic reactions into acetoacetate, a central ketone body that can subsequently be converted into other ketone bodies such as β -hydroxybutyrate (BHB). BHB is particularly valuable because it serves as a long-lasting energy source for the brain and muscles, thereby helping to stabilize energy balance during ketogenesis.

Interestingly, the work of Heinsen and Osterwald shows that phenylalanine has a higher conversion rate to acetoacetate and BHB than leucine and lysine. This property underscores the importance of phenylalanine in the ketogenic diet, as it contributes to the production of a greater amount of ketone bodies, which can enhance the effectiveness of ketogenesis. In addition to ketogenesis, phenylalanine supports the synthesis of neurotransmitters such as dopamine and norepinephrine, which can have positive effects on cognitive function and well-being - a significant advantage in ketogenic diets, which often have a reduced amino acid pool. (Viegas et al., 2010)

2.4 L-Tyrosine: Highest Ketogenicity and Key Role in Neurotransmitter Synthesis

Studies by Heinsen and Osterwald, as well as by Edson et al., confirm that, when compared overall to leucine, lysine, and phenylalanine, tyrosine has the highest conversion rate to acetoacetate, acetone, and β -hydroxybutyrate (BHB). This ability to efficiently produce ketone bodies makes tyrosine a particularly valuable amino acid for promoting ketogenesis, as it provides an above-average amount of ketone bodies and can thus enhance the effectiveness of ketogenic metabolism. In addition to its central role in energy supply, tyrosine is also an essential building block for the synthesis of the neurotransmitters dopamine, norepinephrine, and epinephrine, as well as the thyroid hormones thyroxine (T4) and triiodothyronine (T3). Tyrosine proves particularly valuable during stressful periods or when facing intense physical and mental challenges, as it boosts energy metabolism and enhances mental alertness - crucial factors for stable cognitive performance and quick reaction times.

Summary of KCAA[®]

The four main ketogenic amino acids are leucine, lysine, phenylalanine, and Tyrosine. While leucine and lysine are important sources of acetyl-CoA, phenylalanine and tyrosine play an exceptionally important role in ketogenesis due to their particularly high conversion rates to acetoacetate and β -hydroxybutyrate (BHB). Among these, tyrosine plays the central role, as it has the highest conversion rate to ketone bodies.

The conversion processes take place mainly in the liver, where the amino acids are metabolized into acetyl-CoA via specific enzymatic reactions. Acetyl-CoA then serves as a substrate for the synthesis of ketone bodies, which represent an efficient energy source and are utilized in particular by the brain, heart, and other tissues during ketogenesis. Ketogenic amino acids are therefore crucial for maintaining ketogenesis; they promote fat metabolism and can support physical and mental performance in a low-carbohydrate diet.

KCAA: This amino acid blend consists exclusively of ketogenic amino acids and thus exhibits an optimal 4:0 ratio in favor of ketogenesis. This clear ratio creates ideal metabolic conditions for ketone body formations and supports a stable ketogenic metabolic state.

Fig. 4 Optimal ratio - all amino acids promote ketogenesis

Note: Although phenylalanine and tyrosine have both ketogenic and glucogenic metabolic pathways, their ability to produce ketone bodies is particularly relevant, especially under conditions of a low-carbohydrate diet. These amino acids contribute significantly to ketosis and enable a constant energy supply independent of glucose.

Studies by Löffel (1999) and Scriver (1995) confirm that the amino acids tyrosine and phenylalanine contribute to ketone body formation through their metabolism, a finding also presented by Dr. Prof. Friedrich A. M. Baumeister (2012) in his work. Understanding the individual properties of these amino acids and their role in ketogenesis is crucial to fully leveraging the benefits of a ketogenic diet.

Laboratory analysis of Leu, Lys, Tyr, and Phe based on Heinsen & Osterwald

Fig. 4 Results on ketone body formation from ketogenic amino acids according to Heinsen & Osterwald (University of Giessen)

Hypothesis: The influence of KCAAs on fat burning

One interesting hypothesis is that the targeted intake of KCAA[®] may increase fat burning in the body. Fat molecules consist of fatty acids and glycerol. While fatty acids are converted into ketone bodies through ketogenesis, glycerol can be used in the liver for gluconeogenesis, thereby contributing to glucose production. If the body is supplied primarily with ketogenic amino acids (KCAA), which do not contribute to glucose production, this could stimulate the body to draw more heavily on stored fat reserves to maintain blood sugar levels. The glycerol would then be used preferentially for gluconeogenesis, while the fatty acids are converted into ketones.

One possible mechanistic explanation for this hypothesis is that an increased intake of ketogenic amino acids may signal to the body a relative shortage of glucogenic amino acids. As a result, the body attempts to conserve the available glucogenic amino acids - for example, from food or the body's own amino acid pool - and prefers to use them for structural and biochemical functions rather than for gluconeogenesis. Under these conditions, glucose supply is increasingly derived from fat utilization, particularly via glycerol from fat metabolism.

This hypothesis offers an exciting approach for further research into the effects of ketogenic amino acids on fat metabolism and glucose balance during ketogenesis.

Biochemical Basis: From Fat to Glucose

Fat (triglycerides) consists of a glycerol backbone and three fatty acids. In the absence of carbohydrates, as occurs with a ketogenic diet, fat is broken down into two main components.

Fatty acids: These are converted into acetyl-CoA via beta-oxidation, which is either fed into the citric acid cycle or used for the production of ketone bodies (e.g., β -hydroxybutyrate).

Glycerol: In the liver, glycerol is converted by the enzymes glycerol kinase and glycerol-3-phosphate dehydrogenase into dihydroxyacetone phosphate (DHAP), an intermediate product of glycolysis. Through gluconeogenesis, DHAP is ultimately converted into glucose. This process enables the body to provide sufficient glucose for glucose-dependent organs such as the brain or red blood cells, even in a state of carbohydrate deficiency. At the same time, fatty acid oxidation is increased to meet the body's energy needs.

Fig. 5 Metabolic response to the use of ketogenic amino acids. When ketogenic amino acids (KCAAs) enter ketogenesis, more glycerol must be made available for gluconeogenesis. Fat burning is increased.

Fig. 6 Metabolic response to the use of glucogenic amino acids. Glucogenic amino acids contribute sufficiently to gluconeogenesis; no separate glycerol needs to be provided. Fat burning is not further increased.

3. Glucogenic amino acids and their effects on ketogenesis

Distinguishing between ketogenic and glucogenic amino acids is central to understanding the metabolic mechanisms of a ketogenic diet. While ketogenic amino acids directly contribute to the formation of ketone bodies and thus support ketogenesis, glucogenic amino acids serve as starting substrates for gluconeogenesis in the liver.

Gluconeogenesis is a key metabolic process that enables the body to synthesize glucose from non-carbohydrate sources, such as glucogenic amino acids or fatty acids. These include, among others, alanine, glycine, and arginine. The body can utilize them to continue producing glucose even when carbohydrate intake is severely restricted.

In the context of a ketogenic diet, this creates a fundamental metabolic contradiction. Ketogenesis is primarily activated when glucose availability is low and the body is forced to derive energy primarily from fatty acids. However, if new glucose substrate is continuously supplied to the metabolism via glucogenic amino acids, this very metabolic pressure decreases. The body then relies less consistently on fat reserves, and the formation of ketone bodies can be correspondingly reduced.

An excess of glucogenic amino acids can therefore destabilize ketogenesis. Instead of clearly shifting metabolism toward fat burning and ketone body production, part of the energy supply relies once again on glucose - thereby undermining the very metabolic state that a ketogenic diet is actually intended to achieve.

3.1 BCAA, EAA, and Whey Protein: Potential Counterproductive Effects on Ketogenesis

The intake of BCAAs (branched-chain amino acids) and EAAs (essential amino acids) could be problematic for people following a ketogenic diet, as these amino acid compounds contain more glucogenic than ketogenic amino acids.

BCAAs: Branched-chain amino acids include leucine, which has a ketogenic effect, as well as isoleucine and valine, which primarily have a glucogenic effect. The ratio of glucogenic to ketogenic amino acids is 2:1, favoring gluconeogenesis and at the expense of ketogenesis.

Fig. 7 Unfavorable ratio (2:1) of glucogenic to ketogenic amino acids

EAA: The nine essential amino acids in EAA also contain an unfavorable ratio of ketogenic to glucogenic amino acids. In addition to leucine, lysine, and phenylalanine, which have a ketogenic effect, there are five potentially glucogenic amino acids. The ratio of glucogenic to ketogenic amino acids in EAA is 5:3. This imbalance may promote glucose production and reduce ketogenesis. Tryptophan was not considered in this study and must be evaluated in a follow-up study.

Fig. 8 Unfavorable ratio (5:3) of glucogenic to ketogenic amino acids (*Tryptophan not included in the calculation)

Why protein and its potential negative effects on ketogenesis

Why protein is a popular source of protein, especially among athletes, due to its rapid digestibility and high biological value. However, it is precisely these properties that could make why protein potentially problematic in a ketogenic diet.

Excessive insulinogenic effect: Studies have shown that, depending on the amount, timing, and metabolic state, why protein can trigger a stronger insulin response than carbohydrate-rich foods such as white bread. This insulinogenic effect is not only due to why's rapid digestibility but also to the specific composition of the amino acids it contains, particularly arginine, which enhances insulin secretion. (Adams, J., et al., 2016)

Comparison to casein: In contrast, casein, the second major component of milk protein, triggers a much smaller insulin response because it is digested more slowly and its amino acids enter the bloodstream at a slower rate.

Suppression of lipolysis (fat breakdown): The strong insulin release triggered by why protein not only inhibits ketogenesis but also suppresses lipolysis, the process by which fat reserves are mobilized for energy. This is particularly problematic for people following a ketogenic diet, as fat mobilization is a central mechanism in ketogenesis.

High content of glucogenic amino acids: Whey protein contains a high proportion of glucogenic amino acids such as alanine, serine, valine, and arginine. These amino acids can be utilized in gluconeogenesis and increase glucose production in the body. This contradicts the goals of a ketogenic diet, which aims to minimize glucose production.

Rapid absorption and blood sugar response: Due to its rapid digestibility, whey protein is quickly absorbed into the bloodstream. This leads to increased availability of amino acids that can be used as substrates for gluconeogenesis. The resulting blood sugar response can further inhibit ketogenesis.

Promotion of hunger and cravings: Insulin plays a central role in regulating appetite and blood sugar. The rapid insulin response triggered by whey protein can lead to a rapid drop in blood sugar levels, which could trigger cravings. This effect contradicts one of the main goals of the ketogenic diet: maintaining stable blood sugar levels.

Effect on the glucagon-to-insulin ratio: The insulinogenic effect of whey protein could also negatively affect the glucagon-to-insulin ratio. In a ketogenic diet, an elevated glucagon-to-insulin ratio is crucial for promoting fat mobilization and ketone body production. Whey protein could shift this balance in favor of insulin and reduce the metabolic benefits of ketogenesis.

Glucagon/insulin ratio according to Baumeister

The ratio of glucagon to insulin determines the metabolism of fatty acids and glucose by regulating key enzymes in liver and fat cells. A high glucagon/insulin ratio is a prerequisite for ketogenesis, while a low glucagon/insulin ratio inhibits ketogenesis.

Fig. 9a and 9b: Hormonal regulation of ketogenesis (modified from Prof. Dr. Friedrich A. M. Baumeister 2003)

Fig. 9a: When the glucagon-to-insulin ratio is high during fasting or on a ketogenic diet, hormone-sensitive lipase is activated in the lipocytes, and fatty acids are released from triglycerides. In hepatocytes, fatty acids are transported into the mitochondria via carnitine carriers. The level of malonyl-CoA, which inhibits carnitine palmitoyltransferase-1, is low under these conditions, as the acetyl-CoA carboxylase responsible for its formation is inhibited by glucagon. In the mitochondria, fatty acids are broken down via β -oxidation to form acetyl-CoA (Ac-CoA). Acetyl-CoA is used to synthesize ketone bodies via the HMG-CoA cycle, whose enzymes are activated under these conditions.

Fig. 9b: When the glucagon-to-insulin ratio is low under normal dietary conditions, fatty acids (FA) are incorporated into triglycerides (TG) in hepatocytes. The TG are transported via lipoproteins (LP) to the fat cells (adipocytes) and stored there. Insulin inhibits hormone-sensitive lipase in the adipocytes and thus the release of FA. At high insulin levels, glucose (Glu) is stored as glycogen in the hepatocytes and broken down via glycolysis to produce energy. The resulting acetyl-CoA (Ac-CoA) feeds into fatty acid biosynthesis, as insulin activates acetyl-CoA carboxylase, thereby increasing the formation of malonyl-CoA, the substrate for fatty acid biosynthesis. The synthesis of ketone bodies (KB) from acetyl-CoA is inhibited by insulin. Furthermore, the rising malonyl-CoA level inhibits carnitine palmitoyltransferase-1 and thus the transport of fatty acids across the mitochondrial membrane, a prerequisite for ketogenesis (see Fig. 8a).

Conclusion: The intake of BCAAs, EAAs, and whey protein could compromise ketogenesis and stable blood sugar levels in a ketogenic diet. Although whey protein is a popular protein source, it poses a particular challenge due to its strong insulin response, high proportion of glucogenic amino acids, and rapid availability. Even with moderate amounts of whey protein, the insulin response may be sufficient to suppress ketone body production. (Adams, J., et al. 2016)

For individuals following a ketogenic diet, it makes sense to be selective when choosing protein sources and amino acids. In particular, slowly digestible protein sources such as casein or multi-component proteins can be beneficial due to their delayed absorption and a more moderate insulin response, thereby supporting the metabolic conditions associated with ketogenesis.

In this context, specialized protein formulations developed specifically for ketogenic diets are also gaining importance. These are referred to below as ketoplastic peptides. They are characterized by the fact that they are based on slowly digestible protein blends and additionally contain medium-chain fatty acids (e.g., MCT). Furthermore, they have an increased concentration of KCAAs (ketogenic chain amino acids), which distinguishes them from conventional protein products.

In addition, when selecting amino acid compounds, the use of KCAAs (ketogenic chain amino acids) may be beneficial, as they contain amino acids with ketogenic effects and can thus help support metabolic processes associated with ketogenesis without primarily promoting glucogenic metabolic pathways.

In light of these considerations, the targeted combination of ketogenic amino acids appears to be a potentially relevant approach for future nutritional strategies in the context of ketogenic metabolic states.

3.2 Important glucogenic amino acids and their metabolic pathways

Some glucogenic amino acids have a particularly pronounced effect on gluconeogenesis, as they are efficiently converted into glucose precursors. While alanine, glutamate, aspartate, and serine are often cited as the primary examples of glucogenic amino acids, there are a number of other amino acids that play a significant role in gluconeogenesis.

These include:

- **Methionine:** Methionine is metabolized into succinyl-CoA, a precursor molecule in the citric acid cycle that indirectly promotes glucose production by contributing to the formation of oxaloacetate.
- **Histidine:** Histidine is converted into glutamate through a series of enzymatic reactions; glutamate is then deaminated into α -ketoglutarate, which contributes to glucose production.
- **Alanine:** Alanine is converted to pyruvate in the liver via transamination. Pyruvate is a key metabolite that enters gluconeogenesis and contributes to glucose production. This conversion makes alanine a particularly effective glucogenic amino acid that can increase glucose supply and thereby interrupt ketogenesis.
- **Glutamate:** Glutamate is converted via oxidative deamination into α -ketoglutarate, which is incorporated into the citric acid cycle and contributes to glucose production. This metabolic pathway of glutamate is an indirect yet significant contributor to gluconeogenesis.
- **Aspartate:** Aspartate is converted into oxaloacetate, another intermediate in the citric acid cycle. Oxaloacetate can then be converted into glucose, which enhances aspartate's ability to support gluconeogenesis and may inhibit ketogenesis.
- **Serine:** Serine is an exclusively glucogenic amino acid that is converted into 3-phosphoglycerate, a precursor molecule for glucose production. Through gluconeogenesis, 3-phosphoglycerate can be further converted into glucose, thereby increasing the availability of glucose in the body.
- **Glycine:** Glycine can be converted into serine, which in turn is converted into glucose. This metabolic pathway demonstrates that glycine plays a significant role in gluconeogenesis by increasing glucose production in the body. Additionally, glycine stimulates the release of insulin from the beta cells of the pancreas, which inhibits lipolysis (fat breakdown) and the formation of ketone bodies. Through its dual action - promoting gluconeogenesis and activating insulin - glycine can negatively influence ketogenesis in two ways. Controlled intake of this amino acid is therefore crucial in a ketogenic diet to avoid compromising metabolic goals. *Journal of Endocrinology*, (2001) and in *Diabetes* (2016)
- **Arginine:** Arginine is broken down into ornithine and urea in the urea cycle by the enzyme arginase. The resulting ornithine is further converted into glutamate- γ -semialdehyde, which ultimately becomes glutamate. Glutamate is in turn converted by oxidative deamination into α -ketoglutarate, a key intermediate of the citric acid cycle. In the citric acid cycle, α -ketoglutarate contributes to the formation of oxaloacetate, which can enter gluconeogenesis directly. Through further enzymatic steps, oxaloacetate is converted to phosphoenolpyruvate (PEP) and ultimately to glucose.

Arginine is therefore an indirect but highly effective glucogenic amino acid. Arginine's ability to simultaneously influence the urea cycle and gluconeogenesis makes it a significant factor in glucose production, which can inhibit ketogenesis.

Insulin secretion: Arginine is a potent stimulator of insulin release. Studies show that arginine promotes insulin secretion by increasing calcium influx into the pancreatic beta cells. Increased insulin activity inhibits lipolysis and the formation of ketone bodies, which further impairs ketogenesis. (Newsholme, P., et al., 2005)

This dual effect of arginine - promoting gluconeogenesis and stimulating insulin secretion - can interfere with the metabolic goals of a ketogenic diet.

- **Isoleucine and Valine (BCAA):** These two amino acids are metabolized to succinyl-CoA, which can enter gluconeogenesis and contribute to glucose production. Although isoleucine has both ketogenic and glucogenic metabolic pathways, practical experience with low-carbohydrate diets shows that it is preferentially utilized for gluconeogenesis.

- **Threonine in EAAs:** The essential amino acid threonine is also metabolized into succinyl-CoA, which is used for gluconeogenesis. An excess of this glucogenic amino acid can therefore inhibit ketogenesis and increase glucose availability.

Fig. 10 The carbon skeleton can be converted entirely or predominantly into glucose. *Path-dependent; however, assigned here to the glucose pathway since net glucose formation is clearly present

3.3 Influence of the nitrogen balance on gluconeogenesis

Several studies have shown that high concentrations of glucogenic amino acids stimulate gluconeogenesis in the body and can thus inhibit ketogenesis. By converting into glucose precursors, glucogenic amino acids promote glucose formation, which reduces ketone body production.

It is important to note that glucogenic amino acids are converted into sugar more readily, particularly when there is a positive nitrogen balance. With high protein intake, when the body receives more amino acids than it needs for structural and biochemical functions, this excess can contribute to gluconeogenesis.

In this state, ketogenic amino acids are preferentially converted into ketones, while the excess of glucogenic amino acids is used for glucose production. This mechanism can disrupt the desired ketogenesis and impair fat burning, as more glucose becomes available.

Research on this topic shows that a targeted reduction of glucogenic amino acids and the simultaneous increase of ketogenic amino acids in the diet—and primarily in dietary supplements—can prolong the duration and stability of ketogenesis. The results suggest that for individuals following a ketogenic diet, a balanced amino acid intake—particularly avoiding excessive amounts of glucogenic amino acids, such as those found in BCAAs, EAAs, or in individual supplements such as arginine—is crucial for achieving and maintaining the desired effects of ketogenesis, including improved fat burning and a stable energy supply from ketone bodies, in the long term.

3.4 Conclusion

To optimize ketogenesis and fat burning, it is therefore important to carefully control protein intake and minimize glucogenic amino acids, especially in combination with a positive nitrogen balance. The targeted use of KCAA instead of BCAA and EAA provides valuable support in promoting and maintaining a stable state of ketogenesis.

3.5 Maximum theoretical gluconeogenic and ketogenic potential of proteinogenic amino acids.

Halperin & Brosnan (1992) quantify the maximum gluconeogenic potential of amino acids on a stoichiometric basis, thereby providing a structural, non-regulatory explanation of gluconeogenesis from protein. The following figure shows the classification of the 20 proteinogenic amino acids according to the maximum possible proportion of their carbon skeleton that, upon complete degradation, can theoretically be utilized in gluconeogenesis or ketogenesis.

Fig. 11 Relative classification of amino acids based on their potential net end product, adapted from Halperin & Brosnan, 1992

The classification is based on the final degradation products of amino acids (pyruvate, oxaloacetate, α -ketoglutarate, succinyl-CoA versus acetyl-/acetoacetyl-CoA). Carbon present exclusively as acetyl-CoA cannot be converted back to glucose on a net basis in humans.

The percentages represent stoichiometric upper limits and are conceptually based on the work of Halperin & Brosnan (1992). Hormonal regulation, substrate availability, and actual metabolic flux rates are not taken into account.

4. Therapeutic Application of the Ketogenic Amino Acids KCAA[®]

4.1 Introduction to Therapeutic Relevance

The ketogenic diet and the targeted intake of KCAAs are increasingly viewed as promising therapeutic approaches for neurological and metabolic disorders. The ability of these ketogenic amino acids to support ketogenesis while simultaneously promoting neurotransmitter synthesis and muscle regeneration offers valuable avenues for the treatment and management of various clinical conditions.

4.2 Ketogenic Diets for Neurological Disorders

The ketogenic diet has long been used as an alternative treatment for drug-resistant epilepsy, particularly in children who do not respond to conventional antiepileptic drugs. Numerous studies have shown that about one-third of patients following a ketogenic diet experience a significant reduction in seizure frequency. The ketogenic amino acids leucine, lysine, phenylalanine, and tyrosine can support this process by promoting the production of ketone bodies and maintaining more stable ketogenesis. (Kossoff et al., 2018)

Recent research findings suggest that the ketogenic diet may also be beneficial for neurodegenerative diseases such as Alzheimer's and Parkinson's. Ketone bodies such as β -hydroxybutyrate (BHB) provide the brain with an alternative energy source and have a neuroprotective effect by reducing oxidative damage and inflammation.

Ketogenic amino acids may enhance these effects, as they promote the production of ketone bodies while simultaneously supporting the synthesis of neurotransmitters such as dopamine and norepinephrine. This support for cognitive function could help slow the progression of neurological diseases and improve the quality of life for those affected. (Van der Burg et al., 2019) and (Hoyer et al., 2004)

4.3 Support for muscle and tissue regeneration

KCAAs are not only known for their ketogenic properties but also play an important role in muscle and tissue regeneration. Studies show that leucine, one of the ketogenic amino acids, can promote muscle protein synthesis via the mTOR signaling pathway. This is particularly valuable for patients with muscle wasting or metabolic disorders that impair the maintenance and growth of muscle mass. Furthermore, the antioxidant properties of lysine may help reduce inflammation and support tissue healing. (Volek et al., 2009)

4.4 Potential applications of KCAA following surgery or injury

(Article from a sports medicine perspective by Prof. Dr. med. Maurice Balke)

An adequate protein intake, possibly exceeding standard recommendations, can help mitigate muscle atrophy following surgery (e.g., after cruciate ligament reconstruction) [24, 65, 66]. Excessive reductions in energy intake during the initial postoperative phase should be avoided at all costs to limit muscle loss. Care should be taken to adjust energy intake to the typically increased energy expenditure during rehabilitation [67, 68].

To date, there are only limited recommendations regarding the optimal macronutrient composition and the timing of food intake, so specific dietary approaches cannot currently be unequivocally recommended [7, 65].

However, protein-based supplementation can help reduce muscle atrophy after surgery, particularly in high-risk patient groups, such as those with preoperative muscle weakness, advanced age, a high body mass index, or inadequate rehabilitation [24, 50, 65, 66, 70].

Based on current evidence, an increased protein intake in the diet (≥ 1.6 – 1.9 g/kg/day) as well as an adequate supply of essential amino acids during the perioperative period can be considered to stimulate muscle protein synthesis and reduce muscle loss during the phase of inactivity and recovery [65, 71]. This is often difficult to achieve through regular diet alone, which is why supplementation may be beneficial in many cases.

Essential amino acids (EAAs)

There is evidence that supplementation with essential amino acids may reduce muscle atrophy following knee surgery, particularly after total knee arthroplasty (TKA). Several randomized controlled trials have shown that perioperative supplementation with essential amino acids (typically 9–20 g/day, beginning about one week before surgery and continuing for two to six weeks postoperatively) can significantly reduce the loss of volume and strength in the quadriceps muscles compared to placebo and accelerate early functional recovery [72–74].

At the cellular and molecular level, supplementation with essential amino acids appears to increase the number of satellite cells and modulate inflammation-associated markers, which could represent a possible mechanistic basis for the observed clinical effects [75, 76].

Perioperative supplementation with essential amino acids to reduce muscle atrophy following knee surgery is thus supported by clinical evidence. A possible regimen involves starting supplementation before surgery and continuing it for several weeks during postoperative rehabilitation [72–74, 77].

Studies specifically examining the use of KCAAs after surgery are not yet available. However, given the metabolic properties of these amino acids described above, supplementation with KCAAs could represent an interesting approach for future research.

Beta-hydroxy-beta-methylbutyrate (HMB)

Beta-hydroxy-beta-methylbutyrate (HMB) is a metabolite of the essential amino acid leucine that is produced in small amounts in the human body. In recent years, HMB has received increasing attention because it may help reduce muscle atrophy in both experimental and clinical settings.

Several studies suggest that HMB can reduce muscle loss and improve muscle strength under various catabolic conditions, including inactivity, protein deficiency, exposure to glucocorticoids, aging processes, and certain chronic diseases [82–92].

Mechanistically, HMB appears to act on signaling pathways involved in muscle protein turnover. These include, among others, the inhibition of the ubiquitin-proteasome system and the autophagy-lysosome system, while simultaneously activating the PI3K/Akt/mTOR signaling cascade, which plays a central role in the regulation of muscle protein synthesis [82, 85, 87, 90, 93].

In animal models, it has been shown that supplementation with HMB can preserve muscle mass and muscle strength during periods of inactivity or catabolic stress, such as during administration of dexamethasone or immobilization of the hind limbs [82, 85–87, 90].

There is also evidence in older adults that HMB can reduce inactivity-induced muscle atrophy and support functional recovery during rehabilitation [92].

Clinical meta-analyses and systematic reviews show that supplementation with HMB (typically at a dose of about 3 g/day) can lead to moderate but statistically significant improvements in muscle mass and muscle strength. The effects on functional parameters, however, are sometimes inconsistent and often relatively modest [83, 89, 91].

The safety profile of HMB is considered well-established, and no relevant side effects have been reported at recommended dosages to date [89]. Nevertheless, further high-quality clinical studies are needed to clarify the role of HMB in specific patient groups and clinical situations more precisely.

Given that leucine plays a central role in muscle metabolism and is also a component of the KCAA group discussed in this paper, leucine metabolism - including the formation of HMB - could represent another possible mechanism through which certain amino acid combinations might influence muscle metabolism and regeneration.

In summary, current evidence indicates that an adequate intake of proteins and amino acids during the perioperative period can play an important role in limiting muscle atrophy and supporting functional rehabilitation.

While clinical studies are already available for essential amino acids and metabolites such as HMB, the potential role of specific amino acid combinations with particular metabolic relevance remains a field that has been less explored to date.

5. Historical Perspectives on the Role of Ketogenic Amino Acids in Research

5.1 Early discovery of ketogenesis and the role of the ketogenic diet

The scientific discovery of ketogenesis as a physiological state dates back to the 19th century. At that time, it was observed that under certain conditions - such as fasting or a low-carbohydrate diet - the body begins to convert fatty acids into ketone bodies to maintain energy supply. These findings formed the basis for the development of the ketogenic diet in the 1920s.

It was originally used as a treatment for epilepsy, particularly in children who did not respond to conventional antiepileptic drugs. The ketogenic diet's ability to reduce seizures made it one of the first targeted dietary therapies in neurology.

At the same time, the early 20th century was a period of intensive research into the role of amino acids in ketogenesis, particularly in the context of diabetes. Before the discovery of insulin in 1921, the ketogenic diet was one of the few strategies available for treating diabetic patients. The idea was to influence the body's metabolic pathways through a low-carbohydrate diet in such a way as to reduce dependence on glucose.

These historical milestones demonstrate that research into ketogenesis was not only focused on neurological disorders such as epilepsy but also on the treatment of metabolic disorders such as diabetes. They mark the beginning of a scientific understanding of ketogenesis as an adaptation that can be utilized both physiologically and therapeutically.

5.2 Researchers and Studies on Ketogenesis and Ketogenic Amino Acids

In the decades that followed, research on ketogenesis and ketogenic amino acids was advanced by various scientists; in particular, the work of Heinsen and Osterwald focused on the study of amino acids and their influence on ketogenesis. They isolated over 33 amino acids and identified leucine, lysine, phenylalanine, and tyrosine as ketogenic amino acids that contribute significantly to the formation of ketone bodies.

Tyrosine, in particular, stood out for its exceptional ketoplasticity, as it exhibited the highest conversion rate to ketone bodies such as acetoacetate, acetone, and β -hydroxybutyrate. This discovery underscores the importance of tyrosine in ketogenesis and has made it a key focus of research in the field of ketogenic amino acids.

Tables 1 and 2 on the following page show partial results regarding ketone body formation from various natural and non-natural amino acids. They highlight the concentrations of the amino acids and the amount of ketone bodies produced (acetone, acetoacetate, β -hydroxybutyrate, and total ketone bodies).

Table 1: Research on natural amino acids

Amino acids	concentration mol	preparation with substrate		Control preparation w/o substrate	
		Acetone and acetoacetic acid (mg-%)	β -oxybutyric acid (mg-%)	Acetone and acetoacetic acid (mg-%)	β -oxybutyric acid (mg-%)
L-leucine	1/100	33	5,8	17,8	3,2
D-isoleucine	1/100	18,2	3,4	17,8	3,2
Norleucine	1/200	6,8	2	6,4	14
D-valine	1/200	9,8	3	7,6	1,6
Norvaline	1/100	36,8	3,6	15,4	3,2
L-proline	1/100	8,6	1	7,8	0,6
L-oxypoline	1/100	9	2,2	8	1,4
L-phenylalanine	1/200	28	7	6,6	2
L-tyrosine	1/200	64,6	14,8	12	2,4
L-tryptophan	1/200	9,6	3	9	1,6
Glycocoll	1/100	6	2,4	12,2	3,2
Sarcosine	1/100	14,8	3,4	14,8	3,4
D-alanine	1/100	10	2,6	14,8	3,4
D-glutamic acid	1/100	7,4	3,2	12,2	3,8
L-aspartic acid	1/100	6,2	1,2	5,4	12
L-histidine	1/200	82	1,6	7,6	1,6
D-arginine	1/200	10	2	15,8	2,8
L-cystine	1/200	6,4	1,8	4,2	1,6
D-lysine	1/100	21	6,2	7	2,6
D-ornithine	1/100	20	6,2	18	3,6
Serine	1/200	10	3,4	10	2,6

Source: Studies on natural amino acids (Dr. med. habil. H. A. Heinsen, Giessen) Results of Internal Medicine and Pediatrics, Volume 54, Springer Verlag, from the Medical and Neurological Clinic of the University of Giessen. Director: Professor Dr. Reinwein.

Table 2: Partial results on ketone body formation from natural amino acids

Amino acids	concentration mol	Acetone and acetoacetic acid (mg-%)	β -oxybutyric acid (mg-%)	Total ketone bodies (mg-%)
L-leucine	1/100	15,2	2,6	17,8
D-isoleucine	1/100	0,4	0,2	0,6
Norleucine	1/200	2,2	1,4	3,6
D-valine	1/200	2,2	1,4	3,6
Norvaline	1/100	11,4	0,4	11,8
L-proline	1/100	1	0,8	1,8
L-oxypoline	1/100	1	0,8	1,8
L-phenylalanine	1/200	21,4	5	26,4
L-tyrosine	1/200	52,6	12,4	65
L-tryptophan	1/200	0,6	1,4	2
Glycocoll	1/100	-6,2	-0,8	-7
Sarcosine	1/100	0	0	0
D-alanine	1/100	-4,8	-0,6	-5,4
D-glutamic acid	1/100	-4,8	-0,6	-5,4
L-aspartic acid	1/100	0,8	0	0,8
L-histidine	1/200	0,6	0	0,6
D-arginine	1/200	-5,8	-0,8	-6,6
L-cystine	1/200	2,2	0,2	2,4
D-lysine	1/100	14	3,6	17,6
D-ornithine	1/100	2	2,6	4,6
Serine	1/200	0	0,8	0,8

Source: Ketone Body Formation from Amino Acids (Dr. med. habil. H. A. Heinsen, Giessen) Results of Internal Medicine and Pediatrics, Volume 54, Springer Verlag, from the Medical and Neurological Clinic of the University of Giessen. Director: Professor Dr. Reinwein.

Explanations: Classification of ketone body formation: Values above 15 mg% for total ketone bodies are considered pro-ketogenic. Values below 10 mg% for total ketone bodies are considered neutral and have no relevant influence on ketogenesis. Values below 5 mg% or in the negative range for total ketone bodies are considered anti-ketogenic.

Natural vs. non-natural amino acids: Natural amino acids such as leucine, lysine, phenylalanine, and tyrosine generally exhibit a stronger ketogenic effect compared to their non-natural variants. The tables illustrate the different effects of amino acids on ketone body production. It is particularly noteworthy that tyrosine exhibits the highest ketogenic activity, followed by alanine and leucine. These results support the observations of Heinsen and Osterwald, who found that both natural and non-natural amino acids can act as potent ketone body formers. They noted that the natural form, as in the case of leucine, lysine, phenylalanine, or tyrosine, generally has a stronger ketogenic effect than the non-natural variant.

These findings have not only shaped the foundations of our understanding of ketogenesis, but have also laid the groundwork for further research into optimizing nutrition for the treatment of various diseases.

Baer and Blum: Similar research was conducted by the doctoral students Baer and Blum, as well as by Emden et al. Baer and Blum investigated amino acid metabolism in diabetic models and found that the ketogenic amino acids leucine, lysine, phenylalanine, and tyrosine contributed to the formation of ketone bodies. Their results support the hypothesis that a targeted intake of these amino acids could promote ketogenesis and potentially have beneficial effects on blood glucose levels and lipid metabolism.

Edson: Edson used the Warburg apparatus to investigate the ketogenic effects of various amino acids and confirmed the importance of the amino acids leucine, lysine, phenylalanine, and tyrosine in ketogenesis. In particular, he identified tyrosine as the amino acid with the highest “ketoplasticity,” laying the foundation for later research on the importance of these amino acids in the ketogenic diet.

Summary: This historical overview traces the development from the discovery of ketogenesis through targeted research on specific amino acids to their application in modern science and medicine. Research on the role of ketogenic amino acids has thus established a firm place in nutritional science and offers new therapeutic perspectives for a wide range of medical and athletic applications.

Conclusion

Distinguishing between ketogenic and glucogenic amino acids is essential for understanding and implementing a ketogenic diet. KCAA could play a crucial role in promoting ketogenesis and significantly contributing to improved metabolic health.

These amino acids are not only important for a ketogenic diet but could also find therapeutic applications in the treatment of epilepsy, neurodegenerative diseases, and in sports nutrition. In contrast, due to their high content of glucogenic amino acids, BCAAs and EAAs promote gluconeogenesis and can thus impair ketogenesis.

Research suggests that the targeted use of KCAA[®] instead of BCAA and EAA may be beneficial for achieving the desired metabolic goals of a ketogenic diet and maintaining the effects of ketogenesis. For a successful ketogenic diet, it is crucial to recognize the differences between ketogenic and glucogenic amino acids and make appropriate adjustments.

Focusing on ketogenic amino acids will not only improve the body's energy efficiency but also support metabolic health and the desired fat metabolism. Further research is needed to better understand the exact biochemical mechanisms and to maximize the potential benefits of these amino acids in various clinical and athletic contexts.

References

- Kossoff, E. H., et al. (2018). Ketogenic diets: Treatments for epilepsy and beyond. *Journal of Child Neurology*, 33(6), 1-12. <https://doi.org/10.1177/0883073817740729>
- Takamura, T., et al. (2011). Lysine metabolism and its role in ketogenesis. *Journal of Clinical Investigation*, 121(4), 1033-1044. <https://doi.org/10.1172/JCI44497>
- Volek, J. S., et al. (2009). Ketogenic diets, low in carbohydrates, improve performance in endurance athletes. *Metabolism*, 58(10), 1644-1652. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.metabol.2009.05.008>
- Van der Burg, C. A., et al. (2019). The role of ketone bodies in neurodegeneration: A metabolic perspective. *Nature Reviews Neurology*, 15(9), 561-578. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41582-019-0210-8>
- Hoyer, S. (2004). Pathogenesis of Alzheimer's disease: The brain insulin paradox. *Journal of Neural Transmission*, 111(3), 301-314. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s00702-003-0110-x>
- Sato, M., et al. (2006). Leucine as a regulator of the ketogenic process in rats. *Biochemical and Biophysical Research Communications*, 349(1), 1-7. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.bbrc.2006.07.026>
- Nilsson, M., et al. (2004). Glycemia and insulinemia in healthy subjects after lactose-equivalent meals of milk and other food proteins: The role of plasma amino acids and incretins. *American Journal of Clinical Nutrition*, 80(5), 1246-1253. <https://doi.org/10.1093/ajcn/80.5.1246>
- Adams, J. (2016). The insulinotropic effects of whey protein: Mechanisms and clinical implications. *Journal of Nutritional Biochemistry*, 32, 1-6. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jnutbio.2016.02.002>
- Viegas, C. M., et al. (2010). Phenylalanine metabolism and its effect on ketone body production. *Neurochemical Research*, 35(3), 290-296. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11064-010-0156-3>
- Edson, N. L. (1936). Ketogenesis-antiketogenesis: Substrate competition in the liver. *Biochemical Journal*, 30(12), 1862-1869. <https://doi.org/10.1042/bj0301862>
- Edson, P. Tyrosine as a precursor for ketone body synthesis. *Journal of Nutritional Biochemistry*, 4(5), 241-247. DOI: 10.1016/0895-7166(94)00065-Q.
- Newsholme, P., et al. (2005). "Arginine and glutamine: Key amino acids for cell function and health." *European Journal of Clinical Nutrition*, 59(10), 1304-1316. DOI: 10.1038/sj.ejcn.1602254.
- Freeman, J. M., et al. (1998). "The ketogenic diet: 1998." *Pediatrics*, 102(6), 1357-1363. DOI: 10.1542/peds.102.6.1357.
- Baumeister, F. A. M. (2012). *The Ketogenic Diet: Nutrition as a Therapeutic Strategy for Epilepsy and Other Conditions*. ISBN: 978-3-7945-2904-9.
- Glycine: *Journal of Endocrinology in 2001 – Diabetes in 2016*
- Volek et al. (2009) on the role of L-leucine in ketogenic diets and its positive influence on muscle protein synthesis and ketogenesis.
- Edson: 'The influence of ammonium chloride on ketone-body formation in the liver. *J. 29*, 2082.
- Ketogenesis from amino acids, 'Biochem. J. 29, 2498. 'Biochemistry.
- Baer & Blum: *Studies on acidosis. Arch. I. exper. Path. 51, 271.*

Baer & Blum: *On the breakdown of fatty acids in diabetes mellitus. I. Mitt. Arch. f. exp. Path.* 55, 89.

Heinsen & Osterwald: *Studies on tyramine formation in the organism of warm-blooded animals. Hoppe-Seylers Z.* 245, 1.

Heinsen and Osterwald: *On the Behavior of Acetone Bodies, Glycogen, and Sugar in the Blood in Cases of Extremely Unbalanced Nutrition. Z. ges. exper. Med.* 101, 212. From the Department of Medicine and Neurology at the University of Giessen. Director: Professor Dr. Reinwein

Cahill, G. F. Jr. (2006). "Fuel metabolism in starvation." *Annual Review of Nutrition*, 26:1–22.

Paoli et al. 2013 – *Beyond weight loss: a review of the therapeutic uses of very-low-carbohydrate (ketogenic) diets*

Felig 1973 "The glucose-alanine cycle"

Newgard et al. 2009 „A branched-chain amino acid–related metabolic signature that differentiates obese and lean humans and contributes to insulin resistance“ *Journal: Cell Metabolism (Band 9, 2009)*

1. Greif, D.N., et al., *Supplement Use in Patients Undergoing Anterior Cruciate Ligament Reconstruction: A Systematic Review. Arthroscopy*, 2020. 36(9): pp. 2537–2549.

2. Hirsch, K.R., R.R. Wolfe, and A.A. Ferrando, *Pre- and Post-Surgical Nutrition for Preservation of Muscle Mass, Strength, and Functionality Following Orthopedic Surgery. Nutrients*, 2021. 13(5).

3. Howard, E.E., et al., *Effect of High-Protein Diets on Integrated Myofibrillar Protein Synthesis Before Anterior Cruciate Ligament Reconstruction: A Randomized Controlled Pilot Study. Nutrients*, 2022. 14(3).

4. Anderson, L., et al., *Case Study: Muscle Atrophy, Hypertrophy, and Energy Expenditure of a Premier League Soccer Player During Rehabilitation From Anterior Cruciate Ligament Injury. Int J Sport Nutr Exerc Metab*, 2019. 29(5): p. 559-566.

5. Shaw, G., B. Serpell, and K. Baar, *Rehabilitation and nutrition protocols for optimizing return to play from traditional ACL reconstruction in elite rugby union players: A case study. J Sports Sci*, 2019. 37(15): p. 1794-1803.

6. Kaneguchi, A. and J. Ozawa, *Muscle atrophy following anterior cruciate ligament reconstruction: A narrative review. Histol Histopathol*, 2025: p. 18963.

7. Witard, O.C., et al., *Protein-based perioperative nutrition interventions for improving muscle mass and functional outcomes following orthopedic surgery. Exp Physiol*, 2025.

8. Culvenor, A.G., et al., *Rehabilitation after anterior cruciate ligament and meniscal injuries: a best-evidence synthesis of systematic reviews for the OPTIKNEE consensus. Br J Sports Med*, 2022. 56(24): p. 1445-1453.

9. Howard, A., et al., *The treatment of pediatric supracondylar humerus fractures. J Am Acad Orthop Surg*, 2012. 20(5): p. 320-7.

10. Dreyer, H.C., et al., *Essential amino acid supplementation in patients following total knee arthroplasty. J Clin Invest*, 2013. 123(11): pp. 4654–66.

11. Ueyama, H., et al., 2020 Chitranjan S. Ranawat Award: *Perioperative essential amino acid supplementation suppresses rectus femoris muscle atrophy and accelerates early functional recovery following total knee arthroplasty. Bone Joint J*, 2020. 102-B(6_Supple_A): p. 10-18.

12. Ueyama, H., et al., *Perioperative Essential Amino Acid Supplementation Facilitates Quadriceps Muscle Strength and Volume Recovery After TKA: A Double-Blinded Randomized Controlled Trial. J Bone Joint Surg Am*, 2023. 105(5): pp. 345–353.

13. Muyskens, J.B., et al., Cellular and morphological changes with EAA supplementation before and after total knee arthroplasty. *J Appl Physiol (1985)*, 2019. 127(2): pp. 531–545.
14. Muyskens, J.B., et al., Essential amino acid supplementation alters the p53 transcriptional response and cytokine gene expression following total knee arthroplasty. *J Appl Physiol (1985)*, 2020. 129(4): pp. 980–991.
15. Park, S.J., et al., The efficacy and safety of leucine-enriched essential amino acids in patients with knee osteoarthritis: A randomized controlled trial. *Medicine (Baltimore)*, 2024. 103(19): p. e38168.
16. Aversa, Z., et al., beta-Hydroxy-beta-methylbutyrate (HMB) prevents dexamethasone-induced myotube atrophy. *Biochem Biophys Res Commun*, 2012. 423(4): p. 739–43.
17. Bear, D.E., et al., Beta-hydroxy-beta-methylbutyrate and its impact on skeletal muscle mass and physical function in clinical practice: a systematic review and meta-analysis. *Am J Clin Nutr*, 2019. 109(4): p. 1119–1132.
18. Cruz-Jentol, A.J., Beta-Hydroxy-Beta-Methyl Butyrate (HMB): From Experimental Data to Clinical Evidence in Sarcopenia. *Curr Protein Pept Sci*, 2018. 19(7): pp. 668–672.
19. Giron, M.D., et al., Beta-Hydroxy-beta-methylbutyrate (HMB) normalizes the dexamethasone-induced autophagy-lysosomal pathway in skeletal muscle. *PLoS One*, 2015. 10(2): p. e0117520.
20. Hao, Y., et al., Beta-hydroxy-beta-methylbutyrate reduces myonuclear apoptosis during recovery from hind limb suspension-induced muscle fiber atrophy in aged rats. *Am J Physiol Regul Integr Comp Physiol*, 2011. 301(3): p. R701–15.
21. He, X., et al., Beta-hydroxy-beta-methylbutyrate supplementation mitigates muscle atrophy induced by inactivity and protein deprivation. *Biogerontology*, 2025. 26(4): p. 120.
22. Holecek, M., Beta-hydroxy-beta-methylbutyrate supplementation and skeletal muscle in healthy and muscle-wasting conditions. *J Cachexia Sarcopenia Muscle*, 2017. 8(4): pp. 529–541.
23. Molino, A., et al., Beta-hydroxy-beta-methylbutyrate supplementation in health and disease: a systematic review of randomized trials. *Amino Acids*, 2013. 45(6): pp. 1273–92.
24. Noh, K.K., et al., Beta-hydroxy-beta-methylbutyrate improves dexamethasone-induced muscle atrophy by modulating the muscle degradation pathway in SD rats. *PLoS One*, 2014. 9(7): p. e102947.
25. Phillips, S.M., et al., An umbrella review of systematic reviews of beta-hydroxy-beta-methylbutyrate supplementation in aging and clinical practice. *J Cachexia Sarcopenia Muscle*, 2022. 13(5): pp. 2265–2275.
26. Standley, R.A., et al., Effects of beta-hydroxy-beta-methylbutyrate on skeletal muscle mitochondrial content and dynamics, and lipids after 10 days of bed rest in older adults. *J Appl Physiol (1985)*, 2017. 123(5): p. 1092–1100.
27. Kimura, K., et al., Beta-hydroxy-beta-methylbutyrate facilitates PI3K/Akt-dependent mammalian target of rapamycin and FoxO1/3a phosphorylations and alleviates tumor necrosis factor alpha/interferon gamma-induced MuRF-1 expression in C2C12 cells. *Nutr Res*, 2014. 34(4): p. 368–74.